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Title Page

Title. Substrate-induced conformational change in cytochrome P450 OleP

Short Title. Structural plasticity of substrate-bound OleP

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Nonstandard Abbreviations:

¹OleP, 8.8a-oleandolide epoxygenase; ²P450, cytochrome P450; ³6DEB, 6-deoxyerythronolide B; ⁴CLT, clotrimazole; ⁵DEO, 8.8a-oleandolide; ⁶L-O-DEO, L-olyvosil-8.8a-deoxyoleandolide; ⁷PEG, polyethylene glycol; ⁸rmsd, root mean square deviation; ⁹P450cam, P450 monooxygenase from *Pseudomonas putida*; ¹⁰MycG, Mycinamicin monooxygenase from *Micromonospora griseorubida*; ¹¹PikC, P450 monooxygenase from *Streptomyces venezuelae*; ¹²EryK, P450 C12-hydroxylase from *Streptomyces erythraeus*; ¹³P450BM3, P450 monooxygenase from *Bacillus megaterium*; ¹⁴CYP119A, P450 monooxygenase from *Sulfolobus solfataricus*.

The atomic coordinates and the structure factors were deposited under the code 5MNV (Structural and functional characterization of OleP in complex with 6DEB in PEG) and 5MNS (Structural and functional characterization of OleP in complex with 6DEB in sodium formate) in the Protein Data Bank Research Collaboratory for Structural Bioinformatics, Rutgers University, New Brunswick, NJ (<http://www.rcsb.org>).

Abstract

The regulation of cytochrome P450 activity is often achieved by structural transitions induced by substrate binding. We describe the conformational transition experienced upon binding by the P450 OleP, an epoxygenase involved in oleandomycin biosynthesis.

OleP bound to the substrate analogue 6-deoxyerythronolide B (6DEB) crystallized in two forms, one with an ensemble of open and closed conformations in the asymmetric unit and another with only the closed conformation. Characterization of OleP-6DEB binding kinetics, also using the P450 inhibitor clotrimazole, unveiled a complex binding mechanism that involves a slow event of conformational rearrangement with the accumulation of a spectroscopically detectable intermediate where 6DEB is likely bound to open OleP. Data herein discussed provide structural snapshots of key pre-catalytic steps of the OleP reaction and explain how structural rearrangements induced by substrate binding regulate activity.

Keywords: Cytochrome P450, Substrate binding kinetics, Conformational heterogeneity, P450 structural dynamics

Introduction

The cytochrome P450 (P450) superfamily consists of a large number of heme-containing monooxygenases, distributed in virtually all organisms, catalyzing the oxidation of organic compounds by insertion of an oxygen atom derived from molecular oxygen, into unactivated C-H or C-C bonds (1). They perform multiple functions on a multitude of structurally unrelated molecules. Many P450s catalyze the biosynthesis of endogenous compounds, such as steroids, vitamins, fatty acids, retinoids and drugs, in reactions that require regio- and stereo-specificity. Other P450s are involved in the metabolism of xenobiotics and drugs, showing pronounced substrate promiscuity (2). Although P450s share common fold and catalytic mechanism, the flexibility and the modularity of specific secondary structure elements surrounding the active site and differing in primary structure confer functional versatility to this superfamily of enzymes. These regions are responsible for substrate recognition and orientation in the active site, along with structural transitions (3).

Structural and functional data, molecular dynamics simulation and multidimensional NMR demonstrated that binding to P450s is often coupled to conformational changes of different extents that allow the enzyme to reach the optimal conformation to perform catalysis (4-11). Nevertheless, the extended versatility of reactions catalyzed by P450s, coupled to the variety of their substrates, makes the mechanism of binding difficult to generalize and only decipherable through a case-by-case analysis. However, for bacterial P450s involved in biosynthesis, a general picture is emerging on a role of the central portion of the I helix in sensing the presence of substrates and triggering major rearrangements (12).

The P450 OleP is a bacterial epoxidase produced by *Streptomyces antibioticus* and involved in the final steps of the biosynthesis of the 14-membered polyketide antibiotic oleandomycin (13, 14). During the first stage of the biosynthesis, a specific polyketide synthase, responsible for assembling an acetate unit to six molecules of methylmalonyl CoA, releases an aglycone intermediate, 8,8a-deoxyoleandolide (DEO). This compound then undergoes the following tailoring reactions, *i*) attachment of L-oleandrose and D-desosamine, respectively at C3 and C5, *ii*) 3'-OH methylation of L-oleandrose by a methyl transferase, and *iii*) regio- and stereo-specific epoxidation at the C8-C8a of the macrolactone ring catalyzed by OleP (**Figure 1**) (15).

The precise timing of the OleP reaction has not yet been fully clarified, but some experimental evidences show that OleP is potentially able to introduce the epoxide function both to the aglycone and to the C3-monoglycosylated intermediates (**Figure 1**), suggesting the existence of parallel pathways in oleandomycin biosynthesis (13, 14, 16, 17). As far as the OleP substrates are concerned, both compounds are not commercially available and are hard to synthesize due to the

presence of multiple chiral sites.

Recently, the structure of OleP in complex with clotrimazole (CLT) showed that the inhibitor bound to the heme iron locks the enzyme in an open conformation. The pre-steady state kinetic characterization of CLT binding revealed that OleP follows a simple one-step mechanism, without accumulation of detectable intermediates (18).

In this work we present the structural and functional characterization of the binding of the substrate analogue 6-deoxyerythronolide B (6DEB) to OleP. 6DEB is the aglycone intermediate of erythromycin biosynthesis. It differs marginally from the natural aglycone substrate of OleP, DEO, since only the methyl group at the C13 is substituted by an ethyl moiety (**Figure 1**) and the activity of OleP on this compound was previously reported *in vivo* (16). Structural analysis revealed that OleP bound to 6DEB adopts both a closed and an open conformation in the asymmetric unit whereas higher ionic strength crystallization conditions induced the complete shift of the OleP-6DEB complex to the closed conformation. The *quasi-pseudo* first order kinetic characterization of OleP binding using 6DEB and CLT, in conjunction with structural data, allows us to propose a mechanism of complex formation. 6DEB binding to OleP proceeds through the accumulation of a spectroscopically detectable substrate-bound open intermediate, that is followed by a dramatic conformational transition upon repositioning of the substrate over the heme.

Materials and Methods

Chemicals: 6-deoxyerythronolide B (6DEB) was kindly provided by Barrie Wilkinson and Rachel Lill (Biotica Technology Ltd., Cambridge, UK). Dimethyl sulphoxide (DMSO), Spinach Ferredoxin, Spinach Ferredoxin NADP⁺ Reductase, NADPH, NADP⁺, Glucose-6-Phosphate, and Glucose-6-Phosphate Dehydrogenase were purchased by Sigma Aldrich.

Protein expression and purification, crystallization, X-ray data collection and analysis:

Recombinant His-tagged OleP was overexpressed in *Escherichia coli* BL21 (DE3) strain and purified as previously reported (18). In order to check sample homogeneity and degree of monodispersion, protein solution was loaded into a BioFox 17/1200 SEC (Knauer-Berlin, Ge) gel permeation column, and eluted at 293 K in isocratic mode in a buffer containing 20 mM Tris·HCl, pH 8.0, 0.2 M NaCl. In this condition OleP was found to be in a monomeric state (18). Co-crystallization of purified OleP in complex with substrate analogue 6DEB was carried out by means of the vapor-diffusion hanging drop method using purified OleP at 19 mg/ml and saturating concentrations of ligand (1 mM) at 293 K. Crystals from two different crystallization conditions gave high-quality X-ray diffraction data and were obtained in: 1) 0.4 M NaCl, 10 mM Tris·HCl pH 7, 22% PEG 3350 (low salt, OleP-6DEB_{LS}); 2) 4 M sodium formate (high salt, OleP-6DEB_{HS}). 10% glycerol was used as cryoprotectant for the latter crystals before freezing in liquid nitrogen.

Diffraction data were collected at 100 K at ESRF (beamline ID14-01, Grenoble, France) and BESSY (Berlin, Germany), beamline ID-14-02 using a PILATUS detector. Three data sets of OleP-6DEB_{LS} from crystals grown in the same drop were merged to increase the signal-to-noise ratio, and subsequently indexed, scaled and integrated using the XDS package (19). High salt condition crystals displayed diffraction patterns typical of multiple lattices. Spots belonging to different lattices were discriminated by using the XDS protocol for indexing of images from non-merohedrally twinned crystals (<http://strucbio.biologie.uni-konstanz.de/xdswiki/index.php/Indexing>) and indexed. Data were finally scaled and integrated using the XDS package.

Crystallization conditions, data collection and refinement statistics are summarized in **Table 1**.

Structure determination and refinement: For both structures, molecular replacement was carried out in order to determine the initial crystallographic phases using MolRep (20) from the CCP4 suite (21). For OleP-6DEB_{LS} complex coordinates of a single OleP monomer in complex with the inhibitor clotrimazole (CLT) (18) have been used as a search model (PDB code 4XE3). The coordinates of a single closed monomer of OleP from the latter structure have been used as a search model in the molecular replacement for the OleP-6DEB_{HS} complex. Nine monomers (A-I) and six monomers (A-F) were found in one asymmetric unit of OleP-6DEB_{LS} and OleP-6DEB_{HS} respectively. Iterative manual and automated refinement of the structures was carried out using Refmac5 (22) in the CCP4 suite (21). Five percent of reflections were excluded from refinement and used for the R_{free} calculation (23). Manual adjustment was performed using COOT (24) with Fo-Fc map contoured at 3σ and the 2Fo-Fc at 1σ . Waters were added into the Fo-Fc map, contoured at 3σ , using the *Find Water* tool of COOT. Geometrical quality of the final models was assessed using PROCHECK (25). The first 11-13 N-terminal residues, depending on the monomer, are missing from the models due to insufficient electron density in this region. The quality of the electron density in both OleP-6DEB structures becomes weaker spanning from the first to the last monomer. This trend is particularly evident in the monomer named I in the OleP-6DEB_{LS} structure that only displays electron density accounting for the 70% of the protein (lack of density for all the β -sheet motif, B' helix and BC-, FG-, JK- and KL-loops). Nevertheless, the differences between copies of OleP-6DEB adopting the same conformations are not significant (monomers in open conformation *rmsd* on C_{α} ranging from the minimum value of 0.475 for monomer D to the maximum value 0.681 of the monomer E using monomer A as a reference in the OleP-6DEB_{LS} structure; monomers in closed conformation *rmsd* ranging from the minimum value of 0.274 for monomer A in the OleP-6DEB_{HS} structure to the maximum value 0.883 of the monomer I in the OleP-6DEB_{LS} structure using monomer C of OleP-6DEB_{HS} as a reference) and are likely to reflect

the quality of the individual electron density maps. Therefore, the better-defined molecule A from OleP-6DEB_{LS} and monomer C from OleP-6DEB_{HS} as representative of distinct conformations of the OleP-6DEB complex (open and closed) were used for structural and comparative analyses discussed in the paper.

Final crystallographic statistics for both structures are shown in Table 1, data extend to 2.9 Å resolution for OleP-6DEB_{LS}, and 2.6 Å for OleP-6DEB_{HS}. No outliers in the Ramachandran plot were identified in both structures. All figures were produced using PyMOL (<http://pymol.sourceforge.net>). The atomic coordinates and structure factors for the OleP-6DEB_{LS} and OleP-6DEB_{HS} structures have been deposited in the RCSB Protein Data Bank (accession code 5MNV and 5MNS, respectively).

Equilibrium Binding Analysis: OleP binding affinity to 6DEB was determined at 288 K by titrating the enzyme (1.5 μM) with increasing concentration of the substrate analogue (from 0 to 100 μM), in 50 mM Hepes and 200 mM NaCl, pH 7.5. Since OleP was purified in the oxidized form and catalysis would require external electron donors, addition of 6DEB results in monitoring only the binding reaction. The stock solution of 6DEB was prepared at a concentration of 26 mM in DMSO. The final percentage of DMSO was maintained below 1%. The adsorption shift of the heme Soret peak of OleP from 417 to 390 nm was followed by collecting UV-visible spectra (200-800 nm) after each substrate addition, subtracting the appropriate blank (26). The dissociation constant (K_D) was estimated using the Kaleidagraph software package. A nonlinear regression analysis was applied to the experimental data to estimate the binding affinity constant, K_D , of OleP to 6DEB using the hyperbolic equation $\Delta AU_{obs} = \Delta AU_{max} [L]/(K_D + [L])$, where ΔAU_{obs} is the absorbance difference, ΔAU_{max} is the maximum absorbance difference extrapolated to infinite ligand concentration, and $[L]$ is the ligand analytical concentration. All data were also globally fitted with the program Prism (Graphpad).

Spectrophotometric assay for enzymatic activity and GC/MS analyses of the epoxidation products: The epoxidase activity of OleP was tested with respect to the substrate-like compound 6DEB. The enzymatic assay to test the activity of OleP to 6DEB was carried out using the system ferredoxin / ferredoxin NADP⁺ reductase as electron donor that uses the cofactor NADPH ($\epsilon_{340\text{ nm}} = 6220\text{ M}^{-1}\text{ cm}^{-1}$) as the source of electrons (27). In a total volume of 50 μL, 5 μM enzyme, 3.6 μM spinach ferredoxin, 1 μM spinach ferredoxin NADP⁺ reductase, 50 mM Tris·HCl at pH 7.5, and substrate (from 0 to 600 μM) were mixed together in a 1 cm light path cuvette mounted on a constant temperature cell holder equilibrated at 303 K. NADPH at a final concentration of 100 μM was added to start the reaction. Initial velocities were measured spectroscopically at different substrate concentrations by monitoring the rate of absorbance decay at 340 nm over time using a

Jasco J650 spectrophotometer in kinetic mode, setting 600 s as run time. Initial rates were estimated by applying a linear fit to the linear region of the time trace, determined to be the first 30 s. Initial velocity data were fitted using the Kaleidagraph software package by following the hyperbolic equation of Michaelis–Menten:

$$v = \frac{V_{\max}[S]}{K_M + [S]}$$

where v is the initial velocity of the reaction, V_{\max} is the maximum velocity of the reaction corresponding to substrate saturation of the enzyme, K_M is the Michaelis–Menten constant, and $[S]$ is the substrate analytical concentration.

In order to analyze the product of the OleP reaction using 6DEB as a substrate, 1 μM of the enzyme was incubated with 100 μg of 6DEB in the presence of 20 μM spinach ferredoxin, 0.2 units of spinach NADP^+ reductase, 1 mM NADP^+ , 7.5 mM glucose-6-phosphate, and 0.8 units of glucose-6-phosphate dehydrogenase in a final volume of 1.86 ml of 50 mM Tris·HCl, at pH 7.5 (27). Three aliquots were taken at 0, 60, and 180 minutes. Moreover, a negative control was obtained preparing the same mix without adding NADP^+ . 620 μl aliquots of each sample were dried under vacuum in a SpeedVac SC110 Savant. Pellet was extracted two times with 100 μl MeOH and 200 μl EtOAc. The supernatants were dried under a stream of nitrogen and were resuspended in 30 μl of CH_2Cl_2 . Then, 15 μl Trimethylsilane (TMS) as derivatization reagent were added. The reaction was heated for 45 min at 353 K and then the solution was dried under a stream of nitrogen and the residue finally resuspended in 250 μl CH_2Cl_2 and directly injected in GC-MS (1 μL). GC-MS analyses were performed on an Agilent 6850A gas chromatograph coupled to a 5973N quadrupole mass selective detector (Agilent Technologies, Palo Alto, CA, USA). Chromatographic separations were carried out on an Agilent HP5 ms fused-silica capillary column (30 m \times 0.25 mm i.d.) coated with 5%-phenyl-95%-dimethylpolysiloxane (film thickness 0.25 μm) as the stationary phase. The injection mode was splitless at a temperature of 553 K. The column temperature program was 373 K (1 min), then changed to 573 K at a rate of 298 K/min, and held for 5 min. The carrier gas was helium at a constant flow of 1.0 mL/min. The ionizing energy was 70 eV (ion source 553 K; ion source vacuum 10–5 Torr). Mass spectra were collected in the full-scan mode within the m/z scan range of 50–700 amu.

The efficiency of OleP in NADPH consumption for 6DEB consumed has been also assessed. In a total volume of 250 μL , 5 μM OleP, 3.6 μM spinach ferredoxin, 2.5 μM spinach NADP^+ reductase, 50 mM Tris·HCl, 0.2 M NaCl, at pH 7.5, and 100 μg of 6DEB were mixed together in a 1 cm light path cuvette mounted in a constant temperature cell holder equilibrated at 303 K. After the addition of 100 μM NADPH, the reactions were run at 303 K. NADPH consumption has been

spectroscopically followed by monitoring the rate of absorbance decay at 340 nm over time using a Jasco J650 spectrophotometer in kinetic mode. The reactions were halted by adding 33 μL of methanol after 300 s, when the initial NADPH was completely consumed. Then, each sample was dried under a stream of nitrogen, and pellets were treated as described above. Then, 15 μL Trimethylsilane (TMS) as derivatization reagent were added. The reaction was heated for 45 min at 353 K and then the solution was dried under a stream of nitrogen and the residue finally resuspended in 250 μL CH_2Cl_2 and directly injected in GC-MS (1 μL). A reliable estimation of the amount of substrate consumed was obtained by comparing the intensity of the peak corresponding to 6DEB at the beginning and at the end of the reaction.

Stopped Flow Measurements: The time evolution of 6DEB binding and displacement experiments were followed by monitoring the change in absorbance on a stopped-flow apparatus. Measurements were performed on an Applied Photophysics SX18-MV stopped-flow instrument using symmetric 1:1 mixing mode. The instrument has a light path of 1 cm, and it can also work in a sequential mixing mode, allowing two sequential mixing events with a pre-set delay time in between, and is equipped with either a photomultiplier or a diode-array for single- and multi-wavelength acquisition, respectively.

Ligand binding kinetics: The time evolution of 6DEB binding was followed by monitoring the change in absorbance at 390 nm on a stopped-flow apparatus. OleP, at a final constant concentration of 2.5 μM , was mixed with 6DEB diluted to the desired final concentration, varying in a range from 0 to 75 μM . The traces were recorded in 50 mM Tris·HCl, pH 7.5, NaCl 0.2 M at 288 K. Control experiments indicated that the presence of 1% DMSO had no significant effects on kinetics. The kinetic traces, obtained by averaging at least three experiments, were analyzed applying a double exponential fit using both the software provided by Applied Photophysics and Kaleidagraph package.

The kinetic of binding of OleP to 6DEB at 288 K was also monitored using the stopped-flow apparatus in the multiwavelength mode. 5 μM OleP was symmetrically mixed with 10 μM 6DEB in 50 mM Tris·HCl, NaCl 0.2 M and 1% DMSO. In this experiment, the instrument was set to acquire over 20 seconds 500 absorption spectra in logarithmic time scale fashion, with a 1 ms acquisition time for each spectrum. To avoid light-induced artifacts, a filter cutting UV light at $\lambda < 360$ nm was employed. Spectral deconvolution was performed by global analysis. When used, global fit analysis of spectra sets was carried out using the software MATLAB by combining curve fit and singular value decomposition (SVD) analysis, according to (28).

Displacement and Double Jump Measurements: Displacement measurements were carried out pre-incubating a solution containing 5 μM OleP with 100 μM 6DEB in 50 mM Tris·HCl, 0.2 M

NaCl, pH 7.5, and 1% DMSO. The complex was rapidly mixed with a solution of the same buffer containing different concentration of CLT (final concentration ranging between 6 and 25 μM) at 288 K. Upon CLT binding, the Soret peak shifts from 392 nm to 425 nm, as due to the displacement of the *type I* ligand 6DEB by the *type II* ligand CLT (**Figure S1**), showing a maximum differential absorbance at 433 nm, where we chose to monitor the displacement event. Kinetic traces collected at 433 nm showed a double transition. The rates for the two phases were estimated applying a double exponential fit to each kinetic trace, obtained by averaging at least three experiments, using the Kaleidagraph software package.

Double mixing measurements in 50 mM Tris·HCl, 0.2 M NaCl, pH 7.5, were also performed by using an Applied Photophysics SX18-MV stopped-flow instrument at 288 K. OleP (10 μM) was pre-mixed 1:1 with 200 μM 6DEB for different delay times (from 0.08 to 4 s) and then symmetrically mixed with CLT at a final concentration of 25 μM in 50 mM Tris·HCl, 0.2 M NaCl, 1% DMSO, pH 7.5. The traces, obtained by averaging at least three experiments, were analyzed using the Kaleidagraph software package. The observed amplitudes were plotted as a function of delay times and fitted to a single exponential function.

Reduction kinetics: The electron transfer rate from reduced ferredoxin (from *Spinacia oleracea*) to ferric OleP bound to 6DEB was measured by following the time evolution of OleP reduction in anaerobic conditions, monitoring the change in absorbance at 450 nm upon CO binding to the ferrous OleP on a stopped-flow apparatus (Applied Photophysics SX18-MV). A solution containing 7.2 μM spinach ferredoxin, 2 μM spinach ferredoxin NADP⁺ reductase, 200 μM NADPH in 50 mM Tris·HCl, 0.2 M NaCl, pH 7.5 was symmetrically mixed with a solution containing 10 μM OleP, 200 μM 6DEB in 50 mM Tris·HCl, 0.2 M NaCl, pH 7.5 at 303 K. All solutions were previously degassed and saturated with CO (final concentration ~ 1 mM). Solutions were loaded into gas-tight syringes and absorbance change was monitored at 450 nm to follow formation of the ferrous-CO complex. The kinetic traces, obtained by averaging at least three experiments, were analyzed applying a single exponential fit using both the software provided by Applied Photophysics and Kaleidagraph package.

Results and Discussion

6DEB behaves as a substrate of the P450 OleP

The OleP activity against 6-deoxyerythronolide B (6DEB) was assessed *in vivo* by Gaisser *et al.* in 2002 (16). Here we performed an *in vitro* characterization of the affinity and of the activity with this substrate analogue using the recombinant and isolated enzyme.

Upon 6DEB binding, the *type I* spectral transition typical of P450 substrates was observed, resulting in a shift of the Soret peak from 417 nm to 390 nm (**Figure 2A**) (26). Equilibrium-binding

experiments were performed at 288 K by measuring the absorbance spectra of OleP, at varied 6DEB concentrations. The titration profile observed at 417 and 390 nm was satisfactorily fitted to a hyperbolic function as expected from a simple two-state equilibrium binding (inset to **Figure 2A**). The dissociation constant, K_D , as estimated from global analysis of 50 different wavelengths, was $5.1 \pm 0.2 \mu\text{M}$. The extent of spin state shift is small; this is not unusual for bacterial macrolide acting P450s (27, 29-31). However we cannot exclude a more pronounced effect upon binding of the physiological substrate(s).

To measure the steady state constants for OleP activity on 6DEB, we performed a NADPH oxidation assay, using the ferredoxin/ferredoxin NADP^+ reductase system as an electron delivery shuttle. Initial rates, as estimated by following over time the absorbance decay at 340 nm due to NADPH consumption, were plotted against 6DEB concentration (**Figure 2B**) and analyzed using the Michaelis-Menten equation, yielding $K_M = 8.7 \pm 1.6 \mu\text{M}$, $V_{max} = 0.077 \pm 0.004 \mu\text{M s}^{-1}$, corresponding to a $k_{cat} = 0.015 \pm 0.001 \text{ s}^{-1}$ (**Figure 2B**). The productive usage of NADPH was assessed by measuring substrate consumption and product formation through a gas chromatography–mass spectrometry (GC-MS) analysis of the reaction mixture (**Figure S2A-B**). We have assessed the electron entry rate from ferredoxin to OleP-6DEB (**Figure S2C**), yielding a value of $(12.3 \pm 0.1) \cdot 10^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$, very close to the rate of consumption of the substrate. One might expect a velocity of electron entry faster than the apparent rate of reaction, since two electrons are necessary for catalysis and we have measured the entrance of the first electron, since we followed CO binding to OleP(Fe^{2+}). Considering that the two electron transfer reactions between reduced Ferredoxin and ferric OleP and ferrous and oxygen bound OleP may differ in affinity, binding site and reaction mechanism, we hypothesize that the entrance of the second electron is considerably faster than the one of first electron, as reported for Putidaredoxin/P450cam system (32). This suggests that the first electron transfer reaction is likely to limit the catalytic turnover. Moreover, the analysis of the total efficiency of NADPH oxidation and 6DEB consumption resulted in a 1:1 stoichiometry. Therefore, the data exclude uncoupling and suggest that the k_{cat} is affected by suboptimal electron transfer from spinach ferredoxin to OleP. Nevertheless, taken together, these data confirm that OleP binds and is active against 6DEB, as suggested by *in vivo* studies (16).

OleP-6DEB structure

Crystals of the OleP-6DEB complex were obtained in two different conditions: i) 0.4 M NaCl and 22% PEG 3350 (low salt, OleP-6DEB_{LS}), and ii) 4 M HCOONa (high salt, OleP-6DEB_{HS}). OleP-6DEB_{LS} crystallized in P1 space group and the structure was refined to 2.97 Å resolution ($R_{work}=23.8\%$ and $R_{free}= 31.1\%$). Nine monomers were identified in the asymmetric unit adopting

two different conformations (**Figure 3A**). In more detail, six copies of OleP were found in an open state corresponding to the one previously observed when clotrimazole (CLT, **Figure S3A**) occupies the active site (*rmsd* on $C_{\alpha} \approx 1.3 \text{ \AA}$) (18). Significant differences (*rmsd* $> 2 \text{ \AA}$) occur at the level of 1) the BC-loop (Arg82-Pro85), 2) the C-terminus (C-term) of the F helix and the N-terminus (N-term) of the G helix (Ser175-Glu188) and the loop in between, 3) the C-term of the H helix and the HI-loop (Leu219-His228), and 4) the β -hairpin β_4 (Gly394-Met395); all these displacements result in a slight closure of the active site when 6DEB is bound with respect to CLT-bound OleP. Notably, Phe84 on the BC-loop rotates of almost 90° following the entrance of 6DEB into the active site, driven by a hydrophobic interaction that the residue establishes with the methyl group at the C2 of the aglycone (**Figure 3B**); the BC-loop follows the Phe84 rotation and moves of $\approx 2.5 \text{ \AA}$.

The remaining three monomers of OleP-6DEB_{LS} adopt a conformation in which the accessibility to the active site is strongly hindered (**Figure 3A**), which we consequently indicate as “closed”. A nearly identical “closed” conformation (*rmsd* on $C_{\alpha} \approx 0.4 \text{ \AA}$) was observed in the six monomers identified in the asymmetric unit of the OleP-6DEB_{HS} structure, where the complex crystallized in the C2 space group ($R_{\text{work}} = 20.8\%$ and $R_{\text{free}} = 25.8\%$). Two main differences between the closed OleP-6DEB_{LS} monomers were observed for some external amino acids, *i.e.* Arg208 (*rmsd* = 2.83 \AA) at the C-term of helix G and in the segment between Val136 and Gly139, with a maximum *rmsd* for His138 of $\approx 2.2 \text{ \AA}$, likely due to the different packing in asymmetric unit.

Closure of the active site is achieved mainly by a large ($\approx 10\text{-}12 \text{ \AA}$) movement of the FG portion (helices F and G, and the FG-loop) and of the HI-loop respectively at the top and bottom of the active site (**Figure 3A**).

The initial omit maps, calculated without inclusion of 6DEB in the model, revealed clear electron density in the active site of all OleP molecules from both crystal forms, corresponding to a single molecule of the macrolide. When the protein is in the open conformation, 6DEB is nearly perpendicular to the protoporphyrin IX ring, assuming slightly different positions, depending on the monomer. This mobility appears to be a consequence of the absence of specific interactions within the active site residues that could constrain the substrate in a unique orientation. In fact, 6DEB establishes only van der Waals interactions with hydrophobic residues belonging to the BC-loop (Met83, Phe84, Leu94), the I helix (Ile243, Ala244, Thr248), the β -hairpin β_3 (Leu290, Val291, Ala293, Gly294, Phe296) and the β -hairpin β_4 (Leu396, Ile397) (**Figure 3C**). Moreover, in open OleP, 6DEB is located at a distance of $\sim 6 \text{ \AA}$ from the catalytic Fe, without displacing the water molecule in the sixth coordination position, typical of the resting state of the enzyme, that provides a hydrogen bond to the C9-OH of the substrate and to the carbonyl group of Ala244 on the I helix (**Figure 3C**).

The electron density of 6DEB in the closed monomers unequivocally locates the ligand deeper in the active site, about 2 Å closer to the heme iron, without variability among the six OleP copies in the asymmetric unit. The closure of the active site creates a chamber that extends the network of van der Waals interactions with 6DEB, recruiting residues belonging to the F helix (Met178 and Leu179) and favouring the formation of the following H-bonds: *i*) C3-OH of the substrate and a water molecule H-bonded with the amine group of Glu89; *ii*) the C11-OH of the substrate and a water molecule, H-bonded with the amine group of Phe296 on β -hairpin β_3 and with the C2A-propionate of the heme (**Figure 3D**, the two water molecules are highlighted in grey).

A closer look to the regions of OleP that contact the ethyl moiety at the C13 of 6DEB (methyl in DEO) to analyse possible structural effects on OleP due to the use of a non-physiological substrate shows that this group is located in a small hydrophobic cavity where no specific interactions or clashes with Met83 and Phe84 on the BC-loop and Leu396 on the β -hairpin β_4 at ~ 4 Å are formed (**Figure S3B**). As a possible aspect of the structural effect of utilization of the alternative substrate, since the methyl group at C13 of DEO would be placed even further from those residues, we may hypothesize that Met83 side chain would assume an alternative conformation, in place of the 6DEB C13 ethyl C2 carbon.

Moreover, differently from the open OleP-6DEB, a set of water molecules detectable only in the OleP-6DEB_{HS} closed structures was identified inside a small pocket lined by the I helix, the BC-loop and the substrate. These waters form a network of H-bonds that connects the two hydroxyl moieties at C3 and C5 of the macrolactone ring of 6DEB with Glu233, Asn236, Met237 and Ser240 on the I helix and residues Glu89, Val93 and Leu94 on the BC-loop (**Figure 3D**). These water-mediated connections further reduce the mobility of the substrate and constrain it to adopt a unique position.

Notably, the slight tilt of 6DEB towards the BC-loop observed when OleP adopts the closed conformation reduces the distance between the C8-C8a bond and the heme iron to ~ 4 Å and induces the displacement of the sixth heme-coordinating water molecule, thus breaking the H-bond contacts with Ala244 and the substrate, which rearranges in a catalytically competent location and orientation (Poulos, 2012).

Since the differences between copies of OleP-6DEB adopting the same conformation (open and closed) are not significant and are likely to reflect the quality of the individual electron density maps (**Figure S4**), throughout this paper we will refer to the better defined monomer A from OleP-6DEB_{LS} and monomer C from OleP-6DEB_{HS} as representative of the open and closed state, respectively. We have thoroughly checked that the individual structural features discussed are present in all independent monomers, when allowed by the quality of the respective electron density

map.

Structural determinants for the open-to-closed transition

The crystallization of the OleP-6DEB complex in the open and closed conformations offers two snapshots along the dynamics of the P450 OleP, unveiling the existence of distinct states explored by the epoxigenase in the substrate-bound form that are associated with the position of the macrolide in the active site. This large structural rearrangement mainly involves secondary structural elements that define the substrate binding region, *i.e.* the F and G helices, the FG-, HI- and BC-loops, and the internal I helix (**Figure 4**).

We have carried out an analysis of the open and closed OleP-6DEB structures in conjunction with open CLT-bound OleP (18) to shed light on the structural determinants and mechanism of the open-to-closed transition. The comparison between open OleP-CLT and open OleP-6DEB_{LS} shows that the specific bulk of the macrolide substrate triggers a contraction of the active site in addition to the notable downward shift of the BC-loop, driven by the rotation of Phe84 which establishes a van der Waals interaction with 6DEB (**Figure 3B**).

Searching for specific interactions between the substrate and the I helix, that in some P450s induce a productive structural transition (10, 33), we found out that when OleP is open, 6DEB mostly contacts the I helix at the level of Ile243, Ala244 and Thr248 (**Figure 4a**). The latter residue represents in OleP the conserved threonine responsible for proton delivery during the catalytic cycle, corresponding to Thr252 in P450_{cam} (34), which is commonly flanked by an acidic residue, namely Glu247 in OleP. In this state, these interactions do not induce the one-turn distortion responsible for the formation of the typical catalytic cleft used for proton delivery in P450s (**Figure S5A**) (34). Unaltered geometry of the I helix was also observed when CLT coordinates the heme iron (18).

On the other hand, in closed OleP-6DEB, both the displacement of the sixth coordinating water molecule and the approach of the substrate to the heme iron reduce the distance between 6DEB and the I helix, inducing a change in the conformation of the main chain of Ile243, Ala244 and Thr248 to compensate for the larger steric hindrance of the ligand (**Figure 4a**). As a result, the carbonyl group of Ala244 rotates and moves toward the I helix tunnel, establishing a H-bond with the side chain of Thr248. As a consequence, the helical organization of the main chain in the Ala244-Thr248 turn is lost, leading to the *i*) distortion of the I helix, *ii*) change in conformation of residues belonging to the helical turn, and *iii*) formation of the canonical P450 catalytic cleft (**Figure S5A**). The carbonyl group of Gly245, which in the open OleP-6DEB_{LS} and OleP-CLT structures forms the intra-helical hydrogen bond with the amine of Ser249, leaves the helical geometry and establishes a H-bond with a water molecule, itself H-bonded also to the side chain of Glu365 on the L helix

(**Figure 4b**). This network of interactions, starting from Thr248 and ending with Glu365, both conserved among P450s, defines the internal solvent channel that allows the access of protons necessary for the catalytic cycle in OleP.

The effect of the I helix distortion induced by productive binding of the substrate is not limited to this local environment. By introducing a kink in the middle of this long helix, the helical distortion represents the epicenter of a dramatic rearrangement of secondary structure elements that expands over the vault of the binding site, leading to its sealing by means of the collapse of the FG-loop over the BC-loop (**Supplemental Movie S1**). We detail below the main structural interactions that connect and amplify the distortion of the 244-248 turn of the I helix leading to OleP closure.

The kink of the helical backbone at the level of the 244-248 segment does not affect the C-term portion of the I helix, but induces a swinging movement and a $\approx 15^\circ$ rotation of the I helix N-term portion (231-248), with a maximum 8.6 Å displacement of the α carbon of Thr230, the first I helix amino acid (**Figure 4a**).

The H helix, coupled to the moving N-term half of the I helix *via* the HI-loop and inter-helical hydrophobic contacts, follows the I helix swing and causes the reshaping of the HI-loop, that folds into an additional helical turn at the C-term of the H helix. As a consequence of the HI-loop shortening, the H helix is lifted and pushes upwards the C-term of the G helix (**Figure 4c**).

The E helix also follows the I helix swing thanks to a head-to-tail interaction with the H helix *via* H-bonds between main chains (Leu160-Leu215, Leu161-Leu216) and main chain-side chain (Gly162-Asp214) as if the E helix behaves like an N-term extension of the H helix itself (**Figure 4d**).

Moreover, the G helix is coupled to the swinging of the N-term half of the I helix by the Asp201-Lys231 (mid G helix- N-term of I helix) salt bridge and by Val235 on the I helix, which is hooked to the G helix within a niche formed by Met197, Met200, Val204 and Asp201. All the aforementioned interactions are conserved in the open and closed structure, indicating that the Val235 hook couples secondary elements during the open-to-closed transition (**Figure 4e**).

The combined action of swing and rotation of the I helix, the lever exerted by the H helix and the shift of the last turn of the E helix have a dramatic effect on the F helix- FG-loop- G helix segment which moves as a rigid body (**Figure 4**, top panels). The H-bond between Ser175 (F helix) and His246 (I helix) acts as an additional link that drives the FG segment rearrangement, as His246 is rotated towards the active site (**Figure 4f**).

The repositioning of the FG segment acts as a lid over the active site entrance and seals it by contacting the BC-loop to Leu179. The latter residue is exposed to the solvent when OleP is open, and, upon transition to the closed conformation, enters into the enzyme cavity to interact directly

with the C4-methyl group of 6DEB, thus participating to the ensemble of interactions that univocally define the position of 6DEB into the distal pocket upon OleP closure (**Figure 4g**). Moreover, the shift of the FG segment determines the disruption of the network of π - π stacking interactions involving Phe171, Phe174 (F helix) and Phe196 and Tyr199 (G helix) packed onto Pro164 in the EF-loop (**Figure 4f**), previously identified in the open OleP-CLT structure (18). The entry and the initial positioning of 6DEB into OleP active site, that leaves the protein in an open conformation (OleP-6DEB_{LS}), has no effect on the arrangement of the abovementioned π -chain (**Figure S5B**), whereas, upon the open-to-closed transition, a marked movement is observed at the expenses of the aromatic residues involved in the interaction thus altering its organization albeit maintaining the cohesion between helices (**Figure 4f**).

To summarize, closure of the active site is observed only when 6DEB is deeply bound into the OleP active site in a position suitable for catalysis. Such transition appears to originate from the interaction of the substrate with the central residues of the I helix and it extends from the I helix to the external HI and FG units *via* a complex ensemble of interactions. The pronounced movement of the phenyl moiety of Phe84 on the BC-loop that follows the entrance of the substrate in the open OleP-6DEB structure allows the closure by the FG-loop, which brings Leu179 onto the substrate. Both Phe84 and Leu179 constrain the position of 6DEB into the active site.

We have checked crystal contacts in the mobile FG- and HI-loops, and we observed that crystal interactions are absent in the open copies or different among the closed copies, indicating that the crystal lattice does not play a major role in inducing the open-to-closed transition.

Therefore, we hypothesize that 6DEB-bound OleP exists in solution in an equilibrium between two conformations, whereby the open form represents an initial binding intermediate that evolves into the closed form, adopting the catalytically competent binding organization.

Substrate binding to OleP proceeds through a multistep kinetics

The structures of the OleP-6DEB complex revealed an open and a closed conformation for the substrate-bound form. It is then reasonable to hypothesize the existence of an equilibrium between the relative conformers in solution. In an effort to validate this hypothesis and to investigate the mechanism underlying substrate binding to OleP, we monitored binding during the pre-steady state using a stopped-flow apparatus, following the heme absorbance increase at 390 nm occurring upon 6DEB binding. Experiments were performed under *pseudo* first order conditions in symmetric mixing mode, by challenging OleP with increasing concentrations of 6DEB.

For all explored ligand concentrations, single exponential fits proved unsatisfactory, suggesting at least biphasic kinetics. The kinetic traces were indeed satisfactorily fitted to a double exponential equation, as judged by the residual analyses (**Figure 5A**). The rate constants of the fast phase

correspond to $k_{on} = (2.3 \pm 0.1) \times 10^6 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ and ${}^{\text{app}}k_{off} = 21.3 \pm 3.8 \text{ s}^{-1}$, whereas for the slow phase, essentially independent on 6DEB concentration, the rate constant was estimated to be $1.59 \pm 0.06 \text{ s}^{-1}$. The sum of amplitudes, characteristic of the fast and the slow phase, changes hyperbolically with 6DEB concentration (**Figure S6A**) and recapitulates the behavior observed in equilibrium experiments. Analysis of this curve allows us to estimate the apparent K_D , yielding a value of $2.0 \pm 0.9 \text{ }\mu\text{M}$, which is in good agreement with equilibrium titration ($K_D = 5.1 \pm 0.2 \text{ }\mu\text{M}$), suggesting the absence of additional phases in the binding time course.

Previous work on other P450s showed that complex substrate binding kinetics, as observed for 6DEB binding to OleP, can be ascribed to the binding of multiple substrate molecules to a P450 enzyme (26, 35-37), rearrangement of the protein into oligomeric structures (38, 39) or an event of conformational transition (10). Inspection of the substrate-bound structures revealed that the active site of the enzyme in both OleP conformers accommodates only one molecule of 6DEB even when it is present in large excess. Furthermore, OleP is monomeric in our experimental conditions, as previously assessed by size exclusion chromatography (18).

Therefore, the complex kinetics observed for OleP-6DEB binding could arise from an event of conformational transition assuming either *i*) the *a priori* existence of a heterogeneous ensemble of conformations that the enzyme explores in solution (conformational selection model) or *ii*) a mechanism where substrate binding triggers the structural reorganization (10, 39-41).

To further investigate the substrate binding mechanism, we followed the displacement kinetics of 6DEB using CLT as a binding competitor. Previous structural and functional data showed that CLT is able to stably lock OleP in an open conformation following a simple one-step binding mechanism (18). Moreover, compared to 6DEB, CLT showed a significantly higher affinity (two orders of magnitude, $K_D \approx 30 \text{ nM}$) toward OleP, likely due to the direct coordination that it establishes with the heme iron (42).

Therefore, the tight binding capacity of CLT to the enzyme with an extremely slow k_{off} , which can be considered an irreversible process on the time scale of the stopped-flow experiment, was exploited to perform displacement kinetic measurements. OleP was pre-incubated with saturating concentrations of 6DEB (0.1 mM), according to the K_D value obtained from equilibrium binding analysis. The OleP-6DEB complex was then rapidly mixed with a solution containing a saturating concentration of CLT and inhibitor binding was monitored at 433 nm over time. In this condition, if the reaction was only limited by the dissociation rate of 6DEB, CLT displacement should result in a single exponential with a rate constant that is the k_{off} of 6DEB. Nevertheless, the kinetic traces of CLT binding were biphasic, suggesting a more complex mechanism for CLT binding to the OleP-6DEB complex with respect to what observed in binding to ligand-free OleP (**Figure 5B**) (18).

Different concentrations of CLT were used in the experiment, ranging from 6 to 25 μM after mixing, but the observed rate constants for both phases were found to be independent from the inhibitor concentration, given the CLT saturating conditions (**Figure 5B**). In this experiment, the fast phase would account for the event of substrate displacement, yielding $^{\text{fast}}k_{\text{obs}} = k_{\text{off}} = 12.5 \pm 2.8 \text{ s}^{-1}$, which is not inconsistent, yet more accurate, to what estimated by extrapolation ($^{\text{app}}k_{\text{off}} = 21.3 \pm 3.8 \text{ s}^{-1}$). The additional slow phase ($^{\text{slow}}k_{\text{obs}} = 2.7 \text{ s}^{-1}$), not observed when CLT binds unliganded OleP (18), could arise from a conformational transition, suggesting the existence of a heterogeneous ensemble of populations that forms when OleP is bound to 6DEB.

This result, combined to the complex kinetics observed for 6DEB binding and to the structures herein reported, suggests that the mechanism of 6DEB binding to OleP proceeds through at least three steps that involve the accumulation of an intermediate where 6DEB is bound and OleP is in an open conformation. In substrate binding kinetic experiments, the fast phase would be due to the entrance of 6DEB in the OleP active site, while the slow phase would account for the conformational transition of OleP induced by 6DEB, resulting in the displacement of the heme sixth coordinating water molecule and in the closure of the active site, as observed in the crystallographic structure, which would induce a further adjustment of the iron spin equilibrium.

In an effort to measure the absorption changes associated to each kinetic phase, 6DEB binding to OleP was investigated by multiwavelength UV-visible absorption stopped-flow spectroscopy and the set of time-resolved spectra acquired after rapid mixing of the protein with 6DEB was analyzed by global fit analysis. According to this analysis, most of absorption changes occur during the fast phase of the reaction and, interestingly, the two kinetic phases observed upon 6DEB binding proved to be associated with optical transitions somewhat similar one each other, yet distinct in shape (**Figure 6**). The latter observation is in line with the hypothesis that the slow phase accounts for a conformational transition in the protein that takes place after 6DEB binding to open OleP, associated with completion of the heme spectroscopic transition.

As further confirmation of our hypothesis and with the aim to directly measure the rate constant for the structural rearrangement that OleP undergoes in the presence of 6DEB, a double-jump mixing experiment was designed to alter the relative populations of the two conformers. The protein was initially mixed with a saturating concentration of 6DEB (pre-mix) and after a variable delay time, the pre-mix was mixed with CLT at a saturating concentration. At all different delay times, the observed time-courses were fitted to double exponentials. As expected, the observed rate constants for both phases were independent of time delays between the first and the second mix (**Figure S6B**). On the other hand, the amplitudes of the two phases displayed a single exponential dependence on the delay times, yielding an apparent rate constant for the conformational transition

of $k_1 + k_{-1} = 2.8 \pm 1.0 \text{ s}^{-1}$ (**Figure 7A**). **Figure 7A** shows that, while the amplitude of the fast phase, accounting for the OleP-6DEB population of molecules assigned to open conformers, decreases with increasing delay times, the amplitude of the slow phase that accounts for the population of OleP-6DEB molecules assigned to closed conformers, increases. The dependence on the delay times of the amplitudes of slow and fast phases of the displacement reaction (**Figure 7A**) allows to estimate also the fraction of open and closed OleP-6DEB at equilibrium. The $A_{\text{slow}}/(A_{\text{slow}}+A_{\text{fast}})$ ratio accounts for the fraction of closed OleP-6DEB, while $A_{\text{fast}}/(A_{\text{slow}}+A_{\text{fast}})$ would represent the fraction of open OleP-6DEB, where $A_{\text{slow}}=0.026$ and $A_{\text{fast}}=0.044$. From this analysis the closed conformation resulted to be almost as populated (40%) as the open one (60%) at the equilibrium, *i.e.* at infinite delay time.

Notably, the observed rate constant for the equilibrium between the open and closed conformation of OleP-6DEB obtained by double mixing experiment ($k_{\text{obs}} = 2.8 \pm 1.0 \text{ s}^{-1}$) is consistent with the rate constant value determined in the displacement kinetics ($^{\text{slow}}k_{\text{obs}} = 2.7 \text{ s}^{-1}$) and it is of the same order of magnitude of the slow phase of the OleP-6DEB binding kinetics ($^{\text{app}}k_{\text{obs}} = 1.59 \pm 0.06 \text{ s}^{-1}$). An overall interpretation of crystallographic and kinetic data of the binding of OleP to 6DEB is given in the energy diagram in **Figure 7B**.

Final Remarks:

P450 enzymes endowed with high substrate specificity evolved a mechanism that leads to confined oxygen activation and to the entrapment of target molecules by means of active site closure with transitions of variable extent, depending on the size of the ligand. Electron entry in P450s is often coupled to substrate binding that also induces the formation of a catalytic cleft on the I helix to generate a proton relay network and the displacement of the H₂O molecule coordinated in the heme axial position (12).

In the case of OleP, we describe how a limited set of short range interactions established by 6DEB on the I helix leads to the appearance of catalytic activation structural signatures and expands within the protein fold, inducing the active site closure by extensive repositioning of secondary structure elements. Entry of 6DEB in the binding cavity, as observed in OleP-6DEB_{LS} open structure, induces the flipping of Phe84 on the BC-loop and a compacting of the active site in a conformation that we interpret as a pre-activation complex and that we assign to the kinetic intermediate detected by multiwavelength stopped-flow experiment. This assignment relies also on the observation that this intermediate allows rapid 6DEB displacement by CLT. Although it is not possible to directly assess the redox activity of the open-bound state of OleP, the presence of water bound to the heme iron in its crystal structure is a diagnostic feature of low spin/low redox potential. Therefore, we

would infer that this form of OleP is not reducible by ferredoxin, and thus it would not contribute to catalysis or to uncoupling.

In conclusion, crystallization allowed us to capture the OleP-6DEB complex in open and closed states, to our knowledge this is the first time that a complex of a P450 with a substrate has been described in the early (open) and late (closed) stages of binding. Structural data allowed us to mechanistically describe the cascade of interactions responsible for the conformational change and to propose an overall model for the multi-step process of substrate binding which is consistent with an induced fit scenario.

Based on our data on OleP and on structures of other bacterial P450s such as P450_{cam}, PikC, EryK, P450BM3, CYP119A and MycG (8, 10, 11, 43-47), we support the mechanism of substrate sensing by the conserved A/G_{n-1}-G_n-XX-T_{n+3} motif in the center of the I helix (12) which allosterically drives transitions within the protein fold as a general feature of biosynthetic bacterial P450s and as the basis of the regulation of potentially detrimental oxygen activation. Consequently, substrate-bound bacterial P450 structures where catalytic competence signatures are missing (*i.e.* water channel and cleft on the I helix, heme pentacoordination), should be considered as pre-activation complexes requiring further rearrangements to reach the competent conformation for catalysis (9).

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Author contributions

CS and BV conceived the study. GP, LCM, CS and BV planned the experiments, interpreted data and wrote the manuscript. GP, AS, GC and CE expressed and purified P450 OleP. GP, LCM and AM performed enzymatic assays and GC-MS measurements. AG carried out diode array experiment and data analysis. GP, LCM, AS, CS and BV crystallized OleP-6DEB and determined

X-ray structures. GP, LCM and BV designed and performed equilibrium and kinetic measurements of OleP-6DEB binding.

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Figure Legends

Figure 1. Scheme of the reactions catalyzed by OleP in oleandomycin biosynthesis.

OleP introduces an epoxide function on both the macrolide DEO and the monoglycosylated intermediate L-O-DEO. The substrate analogue 6DEB (top left) differs from DEO only for the substituent group at C13, where it brings an ethyl moiety in the place of a methyl moiety.

Figure 2. OleP binding affinity and epoxygenase activity on 6DEB. A.

Equilibrium binding analysis. Difference spectral changes observed upon 6DEB binding are reported. Substrate binding to OleP induces the typical *type I* spectral shift of the Soret band, with a peak at 390 nm and a trough at 417 nm. The inset reports the absorbance changes at 417 (full dots) and 390 nm (empty dots) as a function of substrate concentration on a logarithmic scale. Data were fitted to a hyperbolic equation (fits are shown as solid lines) to determine the $K_D = 5.1 \pm 0.2 \mu\text{M}$ at 288 K. **B.** Michaelis-Menten plot of 6DEB epoxygenation catalyzed by OleP. The initial rates were determined by applying a linear fit to the linear region of the time trace (first 30s). In each experiment, absorbance was monitored at 340 nm by following the NADPH consumption over time at 303 K in 50 mM Tris-HCl, 0.2 M NaCl, pH 7.5. Error bars represent the standard deviation on initial rates of three independent experiments.

Figure 3. OleP-6DEB complex. A.

Superposition of the open (green) and closed (wheat) conformations of OleP-6DEB complex, shown in a non-standard orientation for P450s that allows clear visualization of the structural transition. Secondary structure elements mainly involved in the conformational change are emphasized. **B.** Superposition of the open OleP-CLT (yellow, PDB 4XE3, (16)) and the open OleP-DEB complex (green) that details the movement of Phe84 occurring upon 6DEB binding. **C-D.** Close-up views of the active sites of open (panel C, green) and closed (panel D, wheat) OleP bound to 6DEB. Residues and waters within 5 Å from the substrate are displayed. Red spheres represent waters. Hydrogen bonds are represented by dashed lines. Waters that mediate interaction between protein and substrate, mentioned in the text, are in grey spheres. Secondary structural elements and amino acids are labeled. In both panels the electron density map ($2F_o - F_c$) contoured at 1σ around 6DEB is also shown.

Figure 4. Structural determinants of the open-to-closed transition of OleP.

At the top, open (green) and closed (wheat) structures of OleP-6DEB complex are superposed and shown in orientations that emphasize the structural transition, highlighting the secondary structure elements mainly involved in the conformational change. Helices are represented as cylinders. Panels **a-g** detail individual regions and aminoacids involved in the transition (**a.** I helix distortion, **b.** functional water channel, **c.** HI-loop shortening and H helix fold, **d.** connections between E and H

helices, **e.** interactions between G and I helices, **f.** π - π chain connecting F and G helices, **g.** collapse of the FG-loop). Red spheres represent waters and hydrogen bonds are represented by dashed lines.

Figure 5. Pseudo first-order kinetics of the 6DEB binding to OleP and CLT displacement

kinetics. A. The k_{obs} of the fast phase (filled circles) and the slow phase (empty circles) are reported as a function of the substrate concentration. The former increases linearly with the concentration of 6DEB, whereas the latter is essentially independent from substrate concentration. Error bars indicate the standard deviation on the k_{obs} obtained by averaging three traces for each ligand concentration. When error bars are not visible it is due to their size being smaller than the size of the symbol used. On the right, the trace as the averages of three independent acquisitions obtained at 19 μ M of 6DEB is shown. The residuals to a single (top) and double (bottom) exponential fit are reported below the trace. Thin line is the fit to a single exponential decay. **B.** The k_{obs} of the fast phase (empty circles) and the slow phase (empty squares) of the displacement reaction of the OleP-6DEB complex with CLT are reported as a function of CLT concentration. Error bars representing the standard deviation on the k_{obs} are shown. On the right, the trace as the averages of three independent acquisitions obtained at 25 μ M of CLT is shown. The residuals to a single (top) and double (bottom) exponential fit are reported below the trace. Thin line is the fit to a single exponential decay.

Figure 6. Binding of 6DEB to OleP investigated by multiwavelength stopped-flow

spectroscopy. A. UV-visible absorption spectra collected over 20 s after stopped-flow mixing OleP with 6DEB at 288 K. Arrows indicate the direction of absorption changes. Inset: absorption changes relative to the last spectrum acquired at 20 s after mixing. **B.** Optical species relative to the fast (solid) and slow phase (dotted) observed on 6DEB binding, as obtained by global fit analysis of the time-resolved spectra shown in panel A. Inset: best fit to double exponentials of the first two **V** columns of the SVD output scaled for their corresponding singular values. Fitted rate constants: $k_1 = 19.3 \text{ s}^{-1}$ and $k_2 = 0.9 \text{ s}^{-1}$.

Figure 7. Double jump mixing experiment and schematic energy diagram of substrate binding to OleP.

A. The amplitudes of the two phases are reported as a function of the delay time between the first and second mix. The amplitudes of the slow phase and of the fast phase (shown in the inset) were globally fitted to a single exponential function, yielding a value of $k_{obs} = 2.8 \pm 1.0 \text{ s}^{-1}$. Since the fast phase of 6DEB binding is complete after 0.08 s, the delay times allow following only the build-up of the OleP-6DEB species that binds CLT with slow kinetics. **B.** Schematic energy diagram showing the binding reaction of OleP to 6DEB. Representative structure of open OleP-6DEB and closed OleP-6DEB are given respectively in grey ribbon representation.

Figure 1

Figure 2

Figure 3

Figure 4

Figure 5

Figure 6

Figure 7

Tables

Table 1. Data Collection, Refinements, Statistics and Validation

Highest-resolution shell is shown in parentheses.

	OleP-6DEB _{LS}	OleP-6DEB _{HS}
Data Collection	PDB 5MNV	PDB 5MNS
	0.4 M NaCl, 10 mM	
Crystallization Conditions	TRIS pH7, 22% PEG 3350	4 M Sodium Formate
Space group	P1	C2
Unit cell (Å, °)	a = 112.50, b = 116.70, c = 123.30, α = 103.90, β = 104.30, γ = 114.70	a = 247.60, b = 110.80, c = 159.10, β = 129.6
Resolution (Å)	121-2.97 (3.17-2.97)	120-2.62 (2.78-2.62)
Total measurements	356364	599678
Unique reflections	101917	98805
Completeness (%)	97.5 (91.8)	99.5 (97)
Redundancy	3.49 (3.54)	6.09 (6.8)
R _{merge} ^a (%)	9.1 (48.6)	10.6 (83.3)
I/ σ (I)	11.92 (2.2)	13.63 (2.03)
Wilson B-value (Å ²)	54.4	42.5
Refinement		
Molecules per asymmetric unit	9	6
R _{work} /R _{free} ^b (%)	23.8/31.1	20.8/25.8
Rmsd values		
Bond (Å)	0.007	0.009
Angles (°)	1.21	1.39
Ramachandran (%)		
Favoured/allowed/outliers ^b	93.3/6.7/0.0	96.0/4.0/0.0

^a $R_{\text{merge}} = \frac{\sum_i \sum_j |I_{i,j} - \langle I_j \rangle|}{\sum_i \sum_j I_{i,j}}$, where i runs over multiple observations of the same intensity,

and j runs over all crystallographically unique intensities.

^bNo Prolines and Glycines.

Supplemental Information

Figure S1. UV-vis spectra and difference spectral changes of OleP ligand free and bound to 6DEB and CLT. A. UV-vis spectra overlay of 1.5 μ M OleP (FeII) ligand free (black), and in the presence of 100 μ M 6DEB (blue) and 25 μ M CLT (green) in 50 mM Tris·HCl, 0.2 M NaCl, pH 7.5 at 288 K. The difference in the spin shift observed in the static spectra is comparable or within the experimental error to the shift observed in the equilibrium experiment shown in Figure 2A. The slight baseline shift of the spectra might be due to some extent of sample turbidity. **B-C.** Difference spectra observed upon 6DEB and CLT binding are reported. Panel B: 6DEB induces on OleP the typical *type I* spectral shift of the Soret peak with a peak at 390 nm and a trough at 417 nm. Panel C: CLT induces on OleP the typical *type II* spectral shift of the Soret peak that occurs upon azole binding to P450s, with a peak at 433 nm and a trough at 409 nm. **D.** Difference spectrum observed upon 6DEB displacement using CLT is reported. The maximum absorbance changes from the OleP-6DEB bound form to the OleP-CLT bound form are observed at 394 nm (trough) and 433 nm (peak).

Figure S2. Epoxygenase activity of OleP to 6DEB: GC/SIM/MS chromatograms of reagents and products and reduction kinetics of ferric OleP in the presence of 6DEB. **A.** Relative abundance peaks of 6DEB recorded at time zero (blue) and after 1 (red), and 3 hours (green) are given. 6DEB consumption and product formation were assessed by incubating 100 μg of 6DEB with OleP in the presence of the reducing system with the addition of the glucose-6-phosphate/glucose-6-phosphate dehydrogenase system to regenerate NADPH at 303 K, as reported in Materials and Methods. The decrease of the peak at 10.64 min follows a time dependent trend, indicating substrate consumption in the course of the reaction. In the inset, the relative abundance peaks of the product recorded at time zero (blue), and after 1 (red) and 3 hours (green) are reported. The appearance of a new peak at a retention time of 11.53 min that increases over the time suggests it to be due to the formation of the reaction product. Neither change with respect to the initial amount of 6DEB nor the formation of a new peak was observed in negative controls. **B.** Common peaks relative to the 6DEB fragmentation profile were identified in the fragmentation pattern of the peak that forms over time at 11.53 min (m/z 73, 115, 171 and 256), thus indicating its derivation from 6DEB, most likely being the oxidized product. **C.** The reduction of OleP was monitored at 303 K by following the change in absorbance at 450 nm upon CO binding to the ferrous OleP. Experiments were done anaerobically under a CO atmosphere by symmetrically mixing OleP bound to 6DEB with ferredoxin/ferredoxin reductase system and NADPH in the stopped-flow apparatus, as described in Materials and Methods. The kinetic trace, as the averages of three independent acquisitions, was fit to a single exponential with 0.012 s^{-1} .

Figure S3. A. Open OleP-6DEB vs. open OleP-CLT: structural comparison. On the left, the *rmsd* on C_α atoms, calculated superposing open OleP-6DEB_{LS} and open OleP-CLT (pdb entry 4XE3, (Montemiglio et al., 2016) structures is reported as function of the residue number. The four regions that exceed 2 Å *rmsd* on C_α carbons are enclosed in squares and numbered: 1, BC-loop (Arg82-Pro85); 2, the C-term of the F helix and the N-term of the G helix (Ser175-Glu188) and the FG-loop in between; 3, H helix and HI-loop (Leu219-His228); 4, β-hairpin β₄ (Gly394-Met395). On the right, structural superposition between open OleP-6DEB (green) and open OleP-CLT (yellow) is shown. The four regions that exceed 2 Å *rmsd* are highlighted by a darker colour, enclosed in squares and labelled following the top panel numbering. 6DEB and CLT are shown as cyan and yellow sticks, respectively. **B. Possible structural effect due to the usage of a pseudo-substrate.** Close-up view of the active site of OleP-6DEB in the closed conformation (wheat). The difference between 6DEB and 8.8a-oleandolide is limited to a single carbon atom (highlighted in the figure) located distally with respect to the site of the enzymatic attack. A closer look to the regions of OleP that contact the ethyl moiety at the C13 of 6DEB (methyl in 8.8a-oleandolide) shows that this group is located in a small hydrophobic cavity where no specific interactions or clashes with Met83 and Phe84 on the BC-loop and Leu396 on the β-hairpin β₄ at ~ 4 Å are found. As a possible aspect of the structural effect of utilization of the alternative substrate, since the methyl group at C13 of 8.8a-oleandolide would be placed even further from those residues, we may hypothesize that Met83 side chain would assume an alternative conformation, in place of the 6DEB C13 ethyl C2 carbon. 6DEB is represented in grey sticks. Residues contacting the C13-ethyl moiety of 6DEB are displayed in orange sticks and labelled. Dashed lines indicate hydrophobic contacts and the distance is reported in Å.

Figure S4. A. Average B-factors (main chain and side chain atoms) vs. residue number. Average B-factors of the main chain and side chain atoms are plotted as a function of residue number of each monomer of OleP-6DEB_{LS} (A-I) and of OleP-6DEB_{HS} (A-F) structures. The best-defined monomers A in the OleP-6DEB_{LS} structure and C in OleP-6DEB_{HS} structure were used as representative for the open and closed OleP-6DEB conformers, respectively. **B. The F and G helices and FG-loop in the open and closed OleP-6DEB.** Close-up views of the F and G helices and the FG-loop in the open OleP-6DEB_{LS} monomer A (upper panel) and closed OleP-6DEB_{HS} monomer C (lower panel) structures showing electron density maps ($2F_o - F_c$) contoured at 1σ in one of the region where the largest structural changes take place.

Figure S5. Helix I cleft and π - π chain connecting the F and G helices: comparison with the OleP-CLT structures.

A. Close-up view on the I helix cleft and comparison between OleP-CLT (open, yellow), OleP-6DEB_{LS} (open, green) and OleP-6DEB_{HS} (closed, orange). Only upon the repositioning of 6DEB and the displacement of the sixth coordinating water molecule, as observed in the closed OleP-6DEB_{HS}, the I helix bends forming the catalytic cleft at the level of the Ala244-Thr248 turn, typical of substrate bound P450s. Residues involved in the network are labeled and represented as sticks. Dashed lines indicate hydrogen bonds. Heme and ligand are represented as lines. **B.** Comparison of the π - π chain in open OleP-CTZ (yellow) and open OleP-6DEB_{LS} (green). Residues involved in the network are labeled and represented as sticks. Dashed lines indicate hydrogen bonds.

Figure S6. A. Pseudo first order kinetics of the binding of OleP to 6DEB. The sum of the amplitudes ($A_{\text{fast}} + A_{\text{slow}}$), characteristic of the fast phase (A_{fast}) and the slow phase (A_{slow}) of the OleP-6DEB binding kinetic traces, is reported as a function of 6DEB concentration. The sum of the amplitudes displays a hyperbolic dependence with 6DEB concentration. The resulting K_D value of $2.0 \pm 0.9 \mu\text{M}$, as determined by fitting data to a quadratic equation, is in good agreement with the value obtained by equilibrium titration ($K_D = 5.1 \pm 0.2 \mu\text{M}$). **B. Double mixing experiment.** Observed rate constants (k_{obs}) for the fast (full dots) and the slow phase (empty dots) are estimated by fitting the recorded traces of the sequential mixing experiment to a double exponential fit and are reported as a function of the delay times. 10 μM OleP (final concentration of 2.5 μM) was pre-mixed 1:1 with 200 μM 6DEB for different time delays (from 0.08 to 4 s) and then symmetrically mixed with CLT at a final constant concentration of 25 μM . The experiment was performed in 50 mM Tris·HCl, 0.2 M NaCl, pH 7.5, 1% DMSO at 288 K. The observed rate constants are insensitive to the increasing of the time delay.

Movie S1. Structural determinants of the open-to-closed transition.